

M.N ROY AND THE CRISIS OF INDIA'S PARLIAMENTARY DEMOCRACY

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M.N. Roy's views on democracy is very closely associated with his notion of New Humanism. By drawing from his practical experiences, he came to realise that the parliamentary democracy so widely debated and practised in India during his times, lacks the true spirit of democracy. He blamed the party system prevalent in India's parliamentary democracy for all the contemporary evils. Political parties as intermediaries between the people and the state tend to negate the very spirit of democracy. He strongly argued that parliamentary democracy ignores the two most important democratic virtues of freedom and sovereignty of man. Thus, he suggested his own alternative conception of Organised Democracy where man will be able to enjoy true freedom and thus shall become the master of his own destiny. To him, an Organised Democracy shall witness the true convergence of the great democratic ideals of freedom, justice and popular sovereignty.

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M.N. Roy is considered as one of the greatest Indian political thinkers who has given a new interpretation to the very concept of parliamentary democracy using the prism of new humanism. The depth and importance of his thoughts on these two important concepts have been under appreciated so far. The more we understand and examine his views on these two concepts, the more we are forced to appreciate their relevance to contemporary times. The current crisis in most of the third world parliamentary democracies including India can be attributed to the utter disregard to the basic notions of the concept of new humanism propounded by M.N. Roy. The two core concepts of Roy's New Humanism- freedom and sovereignty of man, so dear to a parliamentary democracy, seemed to be on the decline like never before under the grab of the so-called welfare state. This paper is a modest attempt at explaining Roy's understanding of these fundamental problems of parliamentary democracy in India as it is practised in our times and discuss the alternatives he provided to make democracy truly a government of the people, by the people and for the people.

Despite being a controversial Indian political thinker, he was greatly revered for giving a scientific exposition to the concept of new humanism and emphasising its importance in strengthening the roots of India's parliamentary democracy. The philosophy of new humanism that formed the springboard of his political thought in the later years of his life made him realise the inherent drawbacks of both communism and parliamentary democracy in doing justice to human nature. To him, human beings by their very nature are quite capable of making the best use of their freedom to enhance the quality of their lives. He expressed his strong confidence that a man with full liberty shall use it for the benefit of the whole society (Jena, 1960). But he had serious reservations regarding the modern democratic thought and practice in ensuring necessary freedom to man.

The central concern of M.N. Roy was to ensure freedom of man in every dimension. He dedicated his whole life to the cause of human freedom. He viewed freedom not as a social or economic privilege, but as something that constitutes an integral part of human living. He strongly appealed to fight against all those forces in society which arrest the growth of man's intellectual freedom. To him, intellectual freedom constitutes the very basic prerequisite for furthering human progress and this in turn facilitates social and cultural progress. He strongly articulated this view in his book, 'Reason, Romanticism and Revolution'.

Despite being a serious student of Marxism, he criticised the Marxian doctrine of merging the individual in the society. He firmly believed that both the society and the state should be viewed as the means to promote individual freedom. His inherent faith in the goodness of man and individual freedom led him to the concept of democracy. He was convinced that only a real democracy can provide a congenial environment for furthering human freedom and shall ultimately pave the way towards ensuring social and cultural progress which is the ultimate objective of man. But here he sounded a word of caution regarding the widely prevalent and the dominant discourse of

representative/parliamentary democracy in the political and constitutional thought of the mid-twentieth century. He said that these democracies only reflect a façade of democracy- which is not real.

Rejection of Parliamentary Democracy

By the late 1940s, M.N. Roy became a vocal critic of the different varieties of anti-colonial politics in South Asia. He had serious apprehensions regarding the introduction of parliamentary democracy in India in the aftermath of India's independence. He justified his apprehensions by citing the failure of democracies in Europe and Asia in 1930s and 1940s. To him, the failure of democracies in these regions can be attributed to the 'discrepancy between democratic theory and practice' (Roy, 1960). In fact, in 1949, in one of his speeches he warned regarding the harmful consequences of democratisation of India at the end of the colonial rule. But this does not mean that he did not have faith in democracy as a form of government. In fact, he lauded the rise of democracy in Europe and said that it has confirmed the triumph of the two most important democratic virtues of individual freedom and popular sovereignty (Roy, 1960a).

While not rejecting genuine democracy as such, Roy was very much concerned about the two fundamental problems of modern parliamentary democracies. The first is the indirect nature of law making and the second is the internal structure of the twentieth century political parties (Parasher, 2024). These problems because of their sheer gravity tend to distort democracy in the newly decolonized countries in South Asia and elsewhere.

M.N. Roy attributed this distortion of democratic theory and practice to the prevalence of party system. According to him, political parties tend to mislead the common people by appealing to their emotions and not to reason and thus employ all unethical means to capture power. So, politics in such societies is reduced to nothing more than a scramble for power. As a consequence, 'the concept of the accountability of the representatives to the people has become a sham' (Mahajan, 1987). He was thus a vocal critic of the party system in parliamentary democracies as the political parties tend to manipulate popular consent because of which neither the common citizens can enjoy real freedom nor the sacrosanct principle of 'popular sovereignty' is given its due weightage. In the wake of the inauguration of the constitution of India in January 1950, he expressed the view that the vast bulk of the population in India was 'incapable of controlling the party which claims to represent it' (Roy, 1960b). He argued that such a parliamentary democracy gives representation to the political parties and not the people. He strongly criticised the working of political parties as intermediaries in between the people and the state. People's power in such democracies are being crushed under the power of the political parties and bureaucracy. This makes democracy and political judgement an elite affair.

Roy thus said that the common man in this kind of defaced and disoriented democracy becomes the ultimate loser of his most precious possession- 'freedom', using which he could excel himself both in his individual as well as social life. In these democracies, the state use to centralise all the powers in the name of promoting overall welfare of the citizens. He said that in these so called 'welfare states', 'the welfare of the individual is purchased at the cost of individual freedom which is more important than welfare' (Mahajan, 1987). Denial of individual liberty in these states thus hits at the very foundation of democracy, making it a rule by the minority. The individual in these democracies is merely reduced to a cog in the vast machinery of the state and thus is unable to live his real life and fails to enjoy the much-deserved creative freedom.

Conception of Organised/Radical Democracy

Roy was thus seriously sceptical regarding the ability of parliamentary democracy to ensure the two most precious values to man- realisation of true freedom and maximisation of unrestricted popular sovereignty. So, he came forward with his alternate model of democracy which he called as the Radical or Organised democracy. According to him, it is based on the diffusion of both political and economic power symbolising the harmonisation of the twin principles of freedom and justice. He argued that these basic democratic virtues can be best ensured only in an organised democracy where man becomes the ultimate guide of his own destiny. He was strongly convinced that man in such a democracy shall get all the opportunity to overcome the catastrophe and find a way out to realise a rational and free

society. Man in such a society becomes an active participant both in the political and economic affairs of the state unlike a parliamentary democracy where he participates only in a passive form.

In his book “New Humanism”, Roy has laid down a true picture of the government machinery in an Organised democracy. Giving the highest regard to the principle of ‘popular sovereignty’, he envisaged the establishment of a hierarchy of People’s committees, starting from the local level to the national level. The total number of members of these committees shall be one-fourth of the total population of the locality. These members shall be directly elected by all the adult voters of the locality who have attended the age of 18 years, and the elections shall be held on an annual basis. These committees shall give expression to the will of the people and thus shall function as organs of direct democracy. According to M.N. Roy, the representatives elected at the higher level shall remain under the control of the primary voters and not the political parties.

Another notable feature of M.N. Roy’s Organised democracy is the introduction of the twin mechanisms of direct democracy, that is, referendum and recall. Since the elected representatives are directly accountable to the people, so they are liable to be recalled by the people in case of non-performance. Roy thus firmly believed that in this system of government, the common masses are effectively empowered to become active participants in the process of governance unlike that of a parliamentary system of government.

According to him, in an organised democracy, men of character and intelligence would come forward to assume leadership positions spontaneously with the sole intent of promoting societal welfare. Participation of enlightened members ensures that politics becomes an arena to find out the ways and means to establish a just and equal society. Unlike in a parliamentary democracy, a radical democracy won’t dogmatise the minds of the individual members and thus the individual would be able to enjoy freedom of intellect. It ensures that democracy becomes not only real but also participatory by moving beyond just the right to franchise. This also ensures that procedural democracy is replaced with substantive democracy.

M.N Roy made it clear that the Radical Democracy should not be viewed as a utopia. Its essence is to trickle down democracy to all levels of society and not just emphasise on voting. Percolation of democracy to all fields of individual life ensures that all members of society can share the privileges and material gains of power, and not just the minority elite as is the case in a parliamentary democracy. This shall ensure the prevalence of economic democracy. Being able to enjoy maximum freedom, man in such a society would be like a philosopher, most learned and highly cultured. Roy envisaged that such a society indeed would be regarded as one of the most adventurous experiments of democracy in the twentieth century.

Current Relevance

A thorough examination of M.N. Roy’s views on Radical Humanism reveals that only a real democracy could provide the much-deserved freedom to man and thus enrich the society and the individual. The distortions in democracy manifested in the practice of parliamentary democracies in some countries including India can be attributed to the prevalence of party system. Seen in the context of the practical experiences of Indian democracy in our times, M.N. Roy’s strong convictions on the role and functioning of the party system and its accompanying evils in India have also proved to be true. Soon after India’s independence, gradually internal democracy within the Indian National Congress disappeared and Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru virtually became the absolute ruler of the country. This led to the centralisation of power, and it reached its climax during the tenure of Ms. Indira Gandhi. Thus, the apprehensions of M.N. Roy that party system and the resultant consequences go against the very spirit of democracy is quite amplified from the very working of Indian democracy in general and party system in particular. In this sense, M.N. Roy can be regarded as one of the rare Indian thinkers to explain the evils of party system in India.

He understood that the consequences of party politics in India would ultimately give rise to anti-democratic politics and thus could have far-reaching implications for the country in the long run. This is also borne out by our practical experiences on contemporary Indian politics. It has brought about a divorce between morality and political practice. Political leaders are openly resorting to all kinds of

unethical means to cling to power. Criminalisation of politics and corruption have emerged as some of the most important threats to contemporary Indian politics. One can find political leaders having criminal background in almost all the prominent political parties. This problem is further exacerbated by the centralisation of political and economic power. Personality based politics and lack of intra-party democracy in the political parties in India have resulted in the centralisation of power. This in turn has resulted in the regimentation of individual's thought and actions, depriving him of the creative freedom which he deserves. Party politics thus, goes against the very spirit of democracy.

Thus, M.N. Roy's philosophy of Radical humanism and his critique of the prevalent forms of parliamentary democracy is not without its merits. He has rightly pointed out that not only the government, but all social collectivities must revolve around man. Man must be the centre of all social groupings.

In his alternate conception of Radical democracy, Roy emphasised upon the principle of devolution of both the political as well as economic power to the common man. Man can enjoy his real freedom only when he is guaranteed the same by the state, and this is not possible in the modern welfare states. In parliamentary democracies, state institutions primarily serve the interests of the political parties, and not the common man. In the name of promoting individual welfare, these states make unnecessary interference in all aspects of individual's life and thereby prevent the true enjoyment of creative freedom that can only guarantee individual and social progress.

Thus, M.N. Roy combined scientific objectivity with ethical idealism in political practice. This aspect of Roy's political philosophy provides a befitting answer to the contemporary ethical crisis of modern parliamentary democracies in third world countries including India. His conception of Organised Democracy is aimed at maximising the realisation of the ultimate objective of popular sovereignty without compromising individual freedom and initiative.

Conclusion

A thorough examination of the working of Indian democracy since independence reveals the truth that M.N. Roy's apprehensions regarding the democratization of India at the end of the empire was not baseless and without fears. His alternate conception of Organised democracy based on a hierarchy of People's committees proves the existence of other equally powerful and competing democratic discourses to democratize India at the end of the empire. It brings home the truth that the so called and much hyped representative institutions envisaged under the globalized liberal democratic norms are leaving the major sections of the people from the ambit of democracy by creating electoral hierarchies. Roy's vision of Radical democracy is aimed at dispersal of self-rule throughout the nooks and corners of India with the objective to ensure genuine freedom to the common man. If implemented in its true letter and spirit, it could prove to be an effective model to ensure the diffusion of democracy to all social institutions by ensuring genuine empowerment of the individual.

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